

On the algebraic treatment of Chaos Magick Theory

Leonardo C. Olyachim

1 Events as states in Hilbert space

We can treat probabilistic events as states in the Hilbert space, similar to the treatment of wave-particle states in quantum mechanics. Let us denote a state $|A\rangle$ which is a probabilistic event which can have N outcomes. We can then decompose the state as:

$$|A\rangle = \sum_n^N a_n |a_n\rangle$$

where a_n^2 is the probability of the $|a_n\rangle$ outcome. The states are normalized from the fact that $\sum_n^N a_n^2 = 1$

2 Magick intent as an operator in Hilbert space

We know from Carroll's second equation of CMT that, if M is the magickal factor, the new probability of an event happening is given by[1]:

$$P_{\text{new}} = P_{\text{old}} + (1 - P_{\text{old}}) \cdot M^{\frac{1}{P_{\text{old}}}}$$

Let $|A\rangle$ denote a state which will be the subject of magickal intent. Let \hat{M}_i denote the operator which has the following effect: The action of the operator is increasing the probability of A transforming into the $|i\rangle$ state. In algebraic notation that can be written as:

$$\hat{M}_i |A\rangle = m_i a_i |i\rangle + \sum_{n \neq i} a_n \rho_n |n\rangle$$

where $m_i a_i^2$ represents the new increased probability. The term ρ_n represents the adequate distribution in which every other outcome's probability decreases.

2.1 The eigenvalue problem of \hat{M}

It was shown how the \hat{M} operator acts on a state. Let us now look at the eigenproblems of the eigenstates. The eigenvalue problem can be written as:

$$\hat{M}_i |i\rangle = m_i |i\rangle$$

The increase in the probability is governed by Carroll's second equation of CMT. This implies that:

$$m_i = 1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{a_i^2}\right) \cdot M^{\frac{1}{a_i^2}}$$

One can also conclude from the axiom of the sum of all probabilities and the fact that $(\forall n) a_n \in (0, 1)$:

$$m_i a_i^2 \geq 1 - \sum_{n \neq i} \rho_n$$

2.2 Multiple \hat{M} operators

Let us assume that a single event is being "attacked" by multiple magick intents. The question which arises is: How does the probability of the outcome events change? In this model we will assume the following:

1. Each operator \hat{M}_i increases the probability of state $|i\rangle$ according to Carroll's second equation of CMT
2. The resulting outcome will stay in a probabilistic state until it is observed
3. The probabilities must be the same in all reference frames

With the previous set of restrictions, we can tackle the problem of multiple magickal intents. Let us denote two magickal intents, governed by operators \hat{M}_i and \hat{M}_j . Their effect is given as:

$$\hat{M}_i |A\rangle = m_i a_i |i\rangle + \sum_{n \neq i} a_n \rho_n |n\rangle$$

$$\hat{M}_j |A\rangle = m_j a_j |j\rangle + \sum_{n \neq j} a_n \sigma_n |n\rangle$$

Let us apply \hat{M}_j, \hat{M}_i to the first and second equation respectively:

$$\hat{M}_j \hat{M}_i |A\rangle = m_i a_i \sigma_i |i\rangle + m_j a_j |j\rangle + \sum_{n \neq i, j} a_n \rho_n \sigma_n |n\rangle$$

$$\hat{M}_i \hat{M}_j |A\rangle = m_j a_j \rho_j |j\rangle + m_i a_i |i\rangle + \sum_{n \neq i, j} a_n \rho_n \sigma_n |n\rangle$$

Subtracting the first from the second equation and multiplying everything by $\langle A|$, one arrives at the expectation value of the commutator:

$$\langle A| [\hat{M}_i, \hat{M}_j] |A\rangle = (\sigma_i - 1)m_i a_i - (\rho_j - 1)m_j a_j \neq 0$$

3 Discussion

As discussed, one can easily transfer from just looking at the change of probability to constructing an algebraic theory which can help us understand the underlying principles of nature through the power of mathematics. This paper only serves as an introductory to this topic. A lot needs to be covered and analysed. A better approach at defining the operator \hat{M} must be found, including finding the commutator between different \hat{M} operators, not their expectation value. Groundbreaking, though from the

author's perspective, currently unachievable, is finding a dynamic equation which better represents the dynamic of an event's probability. An equation which evolves through time.

Lastly, it would also be groundbreaking, maybe by the same order of magnitude as the equation in the previous discussion, to find a way of measuring \hat{M} .

References

- [1] Peter J. Carroll. *Liber Kaos*. 1992.